

NEEDS ASSESSMENT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A LEARNING KIT ON LOCAL HISTORY AND CULTURAL HERITAGE IN BALILIHAN

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to conduct a needs assessment as the initial step toward developing a learning kit for teaching local history and cultural heritage in the municipality of Balilihan, Bohol. Anchored on the goal of promoting contextualized and culturally responsive education, the research sought to identify the most relevant historical topics and cultural heritage elements that should be included in future instructional materials. A quantitative approach using a descriptive-developmental research design was utilized to establish an empirical basis for conducting a needs assessment grounded in a review of historical and cultural sources. The instrument consisted of two parts: a Topic Importance Rating on Balilihan's local history—categorized into the Origin, Spanish, American, Wartime, and Post-war and Contemporary periods—and an assessment of cultural heritage assets, where respondents selected the five most significant heritage elements from categories such as Natural, Movable, Built, Intangible, and Significant Personalities and Institutions. The results indicated that cultural experts perceived all historical periods and topics as highly needed, emphasizing a strong and consistent demand to integrate Balilihan's local history into educational efforts. Likewise, the assessment identified key cultural heritage assets, including significant churches, landmarks, festivals, and natural sites, that were most valued by the respondents. It is concluded that there is a compelling and urgent need to develop a learning kit based on these findings. The needs assessment proved to be a crucial foundation in informing educational priorities and emphasized the role of education in preserving cultural memory.

Keywords: *cultural heritage, learning kit, local history, needs assessment*

INTRODUCTION

Cultural educators play a pivotal role in strengthening students' history and cultural heritage awareness and, therefore, are essential advocates in preserving and promoting it in creating spaces where this knowledge is valued and passed on to future generations (Abdallah et al, 2023).

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization has emphasized the relevance of historical and cultural awareness as key components of education and sustainable development (UNESCO, 2009). However, various surveys and studies have indicated challenges and disconnection of Filipinos from their local heritage and history. Factors such as the education system, inadequate documentation, media representation, and globalization contribute to this gap (NEDA, 2017).

Consequently, the province of Bohol has a larger number of National Cultural Treasures (NCT) and Important Cultural Properties (ICP) in the country, recognized and supported by the National Historical Commission of the Philippines (Bohol National Museum, 2018).

Integrating local history into the curriculum plays a crucial role in reconstructing and identifying local identities, considering cultural elements, as a way to mitigate the impact of globalization on identity. Thus, local history education contributes significantly to heritage education and memory building, aiding in the construction of relevant identities among students (Sariyatun and Marpelina, 2024).

Heritage preservation is a key educational responsibility. Global institutions like UNESCO emphasize the importance of safeguarding cultural and natural heritage, highlighting its potential to enrich learning (Lakerveld & Gussen, 2009). Teaching local history and culture makes learning more meaningful, motivating, and participatory—qualities that improve both student engagement and teacher effectiveness (Pedroso et al., 2023).

Anchored on the Republic Act No. 10066 or the "National Cultural Heritage Act of 2009," inspired by Article XIV of the 1987 Constitution, mandates the preservation and promotion of cultural heritage, ensuring community participation and policy support. Its objectives include protecting local histories and cultural institutions and supporting cultural workers.

In light of this, conducting a needs assessment becomes a crucial first step toward the development of a learning kit. It ensures that the instructional content is grounded in the actual needs, interests, and cultural realities of the learners and community. This process guarantees that the resulting learning materials will not only be educationally relevant and engaging but also aligned with national heritage goals and responsive to the unique historical and cultural context of Balilihan.

Developing digital instructional materials should be grounded in a comprehensive assessment of actual learning needs rather than assumptions, ensuring that educational

content aligns with learners' specific contexts and requirements. This approach enhances engagement and effectiveness by addressing the unique needs of the target audience. For instance, a study by Ysulan (2021) assessed Grade 10 students' knowledge of local history and culture, revealing that learners' awareness varied based on factors such as sex, type of school, and family income. The findings underscored the necessity of tailoring educational materials to address identified learning gaps and contextual differences.

Furthermore, despite recognizing local history's importance, there is a lack of systematic studies identifying specific learning gaps in this area. For example, research by Awa-ao and Roperez (2024) explored K-12 elementary teachers' experiences in teaching Philippine and local history, highlighting challenges such as inadequate learning materials and a lack of training. These challenges point to significant gaps in both teaching resources and students' historical understanding, emphasizing the need for targeted educational interventions.

Addressing these gaps requires a data-driven approach that incorporates thorough needs assessments, ensuring that digital instructional materials are not only relevant but also effective in enhancing learners' knowledge and appreciation of their local history and cultural heritage.

Identifying priority topics for digital instructional materials is essential to ensure that the content is relevant, meaningful, and aligned with learners' actual interests and knowledge gaps. A needs assessment allows educators to tailor educational resources to the specific needs of their students, enhancing engagement and learning outcomes.

For instance, a study on developing localized digital learning modules for Indigenous Peoples' health education in the Philippines emphasized the importance of conducting a needs analysis to create culturally appropriate and effective learning materials. The research highlighted that involving local educators and community members in the development process ensures that the content resonates with the learners and addresses their unique contexts and challenges (Tolentino et al, 2020).

Similarly, the study "Needs Analysis of Character Education-Based Local History Learning Resources" focused on integrating character education into local history lessons. By involving students, lecturers, and education program heads in the needs assessment, the research identified key local character values to be incorporated into learning materials. This approach ensured that the developed resources were culturally relevant and aligned with the community's values, thereby enhancing the educational experience (Bahri, 2023). These studies underscore the importance of conducting thorough needs assessments to develop digital instructional materials that are engaging, culturally relevant, and tailored to learners' actual interests and knowledge gaps.

To address existing gaps such as curriculum limitations, lack of localized resources, and the weakening connection to cultural identity, this study was conducted as a needs assessment, serving as the foundational step toward the future development of a learning kit for teaching the local history and cultural heritage of Balilihan. The assessment aimed

to identify the most relevant topics, content areas, and heritage elements that should be prioritized in designing instructional materials.

By grounding future content development in the actual needs and interests of learners, as revealed through this needs assessment, the envisioned learning kit will be more contextually relevant, engaging, and pedagogically effective. The findings of this study can guide the creation of educational resources that align with learners' cultural realities and provide a framework for integrating localized content.

Moreover, the anticipated learning kit, once developed, has the potential to not only enrich educational experiences but also serve as a platform for preserving and promoting Balilihan's local history and heritage. This ensures both accessibility and cultural continuity for current learners and future generations.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to conduct a needs assessment as the initial step toward the development of a digitized learning kit for teaching local history and cultural heritage in Balilihan. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What learning focus of topics are needed in the proposed learning kit based on the needs assessment results in terms of:
 - 1.1 local history, and
 - 1.2 cultural heritage?
2. What recommendations can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative approach using a descriptive-developmental research design to establish an empirical basis for conducting a needs assessment as the initial step toward the development of a learning kit for teaching local history and cultural heritage in Balilihan.

Research Environment

This study was conducted in the historically and culturally rich municipality of Balilihan, Bohol, composed of 31 barangays known for their historical significance and diverse cultural heritage. Balilihan has been recognized by the National Museum of the Philippines, with several heritages declared as Important Cultural Properties. However, the municipality's resource for printed historical data is limited, with the last publication dating back to 2003.

This limited availability of readily accessible historical information further underscores the

need for this study. It provides a rich context for exploring local history and cultural heritage education, highlighting the origin, in which the town's history was intertwined with the Spanish and American colonial periods, with evident historical sites, natural attractions such as picturesque waterfalls, and various cultural festivities and activities.

Research Participants

Through purposive sampling, a total of six (6) cultural experts were chosen purposively because of their expertise in the field for more than ten years. They comprised the Local Government Unit personnel in Balilihan, cultural mapper, cultural bearer, school administrator of Balilihan District, and Social Studies and UCSP teachers, who are involved in participating in the needs assessment for the development of the kit.

The abovementioned participants respectively have responsibilities related to education, culture, or tourism; experiences in documenting and preserving local history and cultural heritage within the municipality; demonstrating knowledge, lived experiences, and authentic perspectives regarding local history and heritage; contributions to curriculum development and implementation; and subject matter expertise and pedagogical practices. These inclusion criteria ensure that participants possess the appropriate knowledge and experience to provide meaningful input in identifying the essential content and focus areas needed for the development of a learning kit.

Research Instrument

To gather data relevant to this study, the researcher utilized a needs assessment approach. The purpose was to identify the key topics needed for the creation of a learning kit focused on local history and cultural heritage. The needs assessment tool was developed based on a thorough review of relevant literature, including historical data, books, websites, and other credible sources.

It consisted of two main components: (1) a Topic Importance Rating for local history, categorized into the following periods: (a) Origin, (b) Spanish Period, (c) American Period, (d) Japanese Period, and (e) Post-war and Contemporary Period; and (2) an Assessment of Balilihan's Cultural Heritage, where respondents were asked to select five (5) heritage assets they deemed most significant for inclusion in the learning kit. The selection was made from a list of cultural heritage categories in Balilihan, namely: Natural, Movable, Built, Intangible, and Significant Personalities & Institutions.

Data Gathering Procedure

The research procedure began with obtaining the necessary permissions from relevant authorities. Once permission was granted, the researcher proceeded with data collection, which was recorded, summarized, and then analyzed. The participants were informed about the purpose of the study, and the introduction was discussed.

The needs assessment was the primary method used to determine the topics and content

needed for teaching local history and cultural heritage in Balilihan. This assessment followed the analysis phase, where a survey was administered to cultural experts to identify educational gaps and areas of interest. The responses from the survey helped pinpoint the most relevant topics to be included in the educational materials. The data collected from the needs assessment guided the selection of the focus areas that are most important for learners in the context of Balilihan’s history and heritage.

Treatment of Data

This study employed statistical methods to analyze the collected data. Data from the needs assessment was tabulated and analyzed using percentage and weighted mean calculations.

Scope and Limitations

The scope of this study focuses on conducting a needs assessment as the initial step toward the development of a digitized learning kit for teaching local history and cultural heritage in Balilihan. The needs assessment served as the primary method for identifying the topics and content necessary for effectively teaching local history and cultural heritage in the municipality. Accordingly, the assessment tool was developed based on a thorough review of relevant literature, including historical data, books, websites, and other credible sources related to Balilihan.

In addition, the participants of the needs assessment were limited to cultural experts—such as personnel from the Local Government Unit of Balilihan, cultural mapper, cultural bearer, the school administrator of the Balilihan District, and Social Studies and UCSP teachers—to ensure that they possess the appropriate knowledge and experience needed to provide meaningful input in identifying the essential content and focus areas for the development of the learning kit.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Needs Assessment in terms of Local History

TOPICS	WEIGHTED MEAN	DESCRIPTION
ORIGIN		
1. Origin of the municipality’s name	3.83	Highly Needed
2. Balilihan as a barrio of Baclayon, territorial changes and annexations	4.00	Highly Needed

3. Formal establishment as an independent municipality	4.00	Highly Needed
4. The first inhabitants of Balilihan	3.83	Highly Needed
5. Origin of each barangay's name in Balilihan.	3.83	Highly Needed
Overall Weighted Mean	3.90	Highly Needed
SPANISH PERIOD		
1. Balilihan as a part of the Spanish colonial system	3.50	Highly Needed
2. Spanish garrison and suppression of the Dagohoy Revolt	3.50	Highly Needed
3. Early settlement and the transfer of the seat of government	3.50	Highly Needed
4. Early leaders or prominent figures from Balilihan's history during the Spanish era	3.83	Highly Needed
5. The construction of the Spanish Belfry and other historical sites and landmarks in Balilihan related to the Spanish colonial period	4.00	Highly Needed
Overall Weighted Mean	3.67	Highly Needed
AMERICAN PERIOD		
1. Balilihan as part of the American colonial system	3.33	Highly Needed
2. Arrival of the Americans in Balilihan during the Philippine-American war	3.50	Highly Needed
3. Leaders or prominent figures from Balilihan's history during the American era	3.67	Highly Needed
4. Governance in Balilihan during the American Period	3.50	Highly Needed
5. Historical sites and landmarks in Balilihan during the American colonial period	3.67	Highly Needed
Overall Weighted Mean	3.53	Highly Needed
JAPANESE PERIOD		
1. Situation in Balilihan during the Japanese colonial period in World War II	3.33	Highly Needed

2. Establishment of concentration camps in Balilihan during the Wartime period	3.33	Highly Needed
3. Leaders and prominent figures from Balilihan's history during wartime period	3.50	Highly Needed
4. Experiences and conditions of the people of Balilihan during World War II	3.67	Highly Needed
5. Role of Balilihons in the events of World War II	3.67	Highly Needed
Overall Weighted Mean	3.50	Highly Needed
POST-WAR AND CONTEMPORARY PERIOD		
1. Impact of Balilihan's social, economic, and political development during the post-war and contemporary periods	3.83	Highly Needed
2. Significant events occurred in Balilihan during the post-war and contemporary periods	3.83	Highly Needed
3. Key figures or leaders that influenced Balilihan's development in the post-war and contemporary periods	4.00	Highly Needed
4. Introduction of the official municipal flag, logo, hymn, and symbols	4.00	Highly Needed
5. Projects and organizations constructed during the post-war and contemporary periods	3.67	Highly Needed
Overall Weighted Mean	3.87	Highly Needed
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN	3.69	Highly Needed

Table 1 presents the results of the needs assessment conducted to identify essential topics in Balilihan's local history, based on responses from cultural experts. The evaluation is structured into several periods: Origin, Spanish Period, American Period, Japanese Period, and Post-War and Contemporary Period, with each period containing specific topics related to Balilihan's history. Each topic is evaluated with a weighted mean, and all topics are considered "Highly Needed." The general weighted mean is 3.69, also indicating "Highly Needed," which is interpreted as a strong necessity for these topics.

The following discussion highlights the most significant topics under each historical era based on the highest weighted means. During the Origin period, two topics received the highest rating of 4.00: "Balilihan as a barrio of Baclayon, including territorial changes and annexations," and the "formal establishment of Balilihan as an independent municipality." These results suggest a strong desire among respondents to understand the political and administrative foundations of the town. Learning about Balilihan's transformation from a

barrio into a fully recognized municipality appears to be vital in shaping a collective sense of identity and civic pride, making these topics essential in any educational material developed for local history.

In the Spanish Period, the topic that garnered the highest rating, with a weighted mean of 4.00, was the “construction of the Spanish Belfry and other historical sites” and “landmarks related to the Spanish colonial period.” This indicates that physical heritage, particularly enduring landmarks that serve as visible symbols of the town’s colonial past, is highly valued by the respondents. The interest in such tangible cultural assets reflects a preference for historical narratives that can be directly experienced or observed, thereby reinforcing the role of visual and spatial memory in historical learning.

For the American Period, two topics were equally rated the highest at 3.67: “Leaders or prominent figures from Balilihan during the American era” and “historical sites and landmarks from the American colonial period.” These results suggest that respondents are equally interested in both the individuals who influenced local governance and progress during this period, as well as the physical structures that represent American colonial presence. The integration of personal stories with place-based learning would thus be an effective approach to developing instructional materials about this era.

In the Japanese Period, the highest-rated topics, both with a weighted mean of 3.67, were “the experiences and conditions of the people of Balilihan during World War II” and “the role of Balilihons in the events of the war.” These findings emphasize the importance of community memory and personal narratives in historical education. Respondents appear to value firsthand accounts and collective experiences of hardship and resilience, which could serve as powerful learning elements in fostering empathy and historical consciousness among learners.

Finally, in the Post-war and Contemporary Periods, two topics received the highest rating of 4.00: “key figures or leaders who influenced Balilihan’s development” and “the introduction of the official municipal flag, logo, hymn, and symbols.” This highlights the community’s recognition of both the contributions of local leaders and the importance of cultural symbols in defining the town’s identity in modern times. These elements not only reflect continuity from the past to the present but also contribute to a sense of unity and belonging, making them integral components of any educational resource about Balilihan’s recent history.

Overall, this implies that cultural experts recognized the importance of understanding Balilihan's local history across different periods and believed that addressing these needs would significantly enhance the learners' and community's appreciation of its historical contexts. The participants gave an overwhelming rating of “Highly Needed” for all the lessons prepared. The consistently high rating across all historical periods reinforces the undeniable recognition of the importance of preserving and teaching Balilihan’s history. This unified response highlights the critical necessity of these topics in developing a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the municipality’s historical context. Evidently, this data emphasizes the urgent need to expand educational resources and

materials to ensure Balilihan's rich local history is effectively recognized, shared, and appreciated by learners and the broader community.

Table 2: Needs Assessment for Cultural Heritage

Balilihan Cultural Heritage Assets	Frequency	Percentage
1. Our Lady of Mt. Carmel Parish & Santo Niño Parish – Hanopol (Churches)	6	20.00
2. Spanish Belfry in Mt. Carmel Hill	5	16.67
3. Sumad Festival	4	13.33
4. Balilihan Town Plaza	3	10.00
5. Kawasan Falls	3	10.00

Table 2 presents the needs assessment result for cultural heritage in Balilihan, listing heritage assets, their frequency, and percentage as ranked by cultural experts. It reveals that the Balilihan churches “Our Lady of Mt. Carmel Parish and Santo Niño Parish” (20.00%), and the “Spanish Belfry in Mt. Carmel Hill” (16.67%) were considered the most significant heritage assets, followed by “Balilihan Town Plaza” (10.00%), “Kawasan Falls” (10.00%), and “Sumad Festival” (13.33%).

Based on the selection criteria of five (5) heritage assets deemed most significant, the results reflect which cultural heritage elements are considered most important by the respondents in relation to Balilihan’s cultural heritage. Balilinhons likely view these heritage assets as essential to their local identity, history, and culture, as they represent the historical, cultural, and social foundation of the town.

These assets encompass both tangible and intangible heritage. Tangible heritage includes natural landmarks such as Kawasan Falls and built heritage like the Balilihan Churches, Balilihan Town Plaza, and the Spanish Belfry, which serve as physical representations of the municipality’s wonders and architectural legacy. The Sumad Festival, on the other hand, represents the intangible cultural heritage of Balilihan, reflecting the community’s traditions, customs, and celebrations.

These heritage assets likely represent the most valued topics due to their deep cultural and communal significance. The Balilihan Churches, for example, are considered focal points of religious and community life, reflecting Balilihan’s spiritual heritage. The Spanish Belfry holds particular importance due to its architectural and cultural ties to the Spanish colonial period. The Balilihan Town Plaza, as a central gathering place, represents the heart of the community, playing a vital role in its social, political, and economic activities. Meanwhile, natural attractions like Kawasan Falls and cultural events like the Sumad Festival showcase Balilihan’s identity, emphasizing the community’s cultural vibrancy and natural beauty. Their significance lies in how they embody the essence of Balilihan’s heritage, making them key to both understanding and preserving the community’s cultural legacy. These selections highlight the broad spectrum of Balilihan’s heritage,

encompassing both tangible landmarks and intangible cultural practices, which collectively contribute to the local community's sense of identity and pride.

Detailed accounts of their cultural significance and community connections are essential in understanding which heritage elements resonate most with the community's values and identity. Overall, the needs assessment results provide valuable insights into the most relevant cultural heritage topics for educational purposes.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that there is a compelling and urgent need to develop a learning kit centered on the local history and cultural heritage of Balilihan. The needs assessment successfully identified the most relevant and meaningful historical periods and cultural assets valued by the community. These findings emphasize the importance of grounding educational content in local identity, fostering historical and cultural awareness, and preserving community heritage.

Furthermore, this study affirms that a thorough and focused needs assessment is an essential foundation for creating educational resources that truly reflect community values. Thus, the needs assessment not only informs content priorities but also serves as a powerful reminder of the role of education in sustaining cultural memory and promoting a sense of identity and pride in one's local roots.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. For the Department of Education to consider reviewing and acknowledging the results of the needs assessment as a basis for supporting the development of contextualized instructional materials that integrate local history and cultural heritage into the curriculum.
2. For teachers to utilize the results of the needs assessment to guide the planning of lessons and activities that are responsive to students' cultural backgrounds and local context, promoting deeper engagement with local history and heritage.
3. For students to encourage active participation in learning experiences related to local history and heritage by engaging with identified topics and cultural elements that reflect their own community's identity, as revealed in the needs assessment.
4. For cultural experts and educators to collaborate in further validating and expanding the findings of the needs assessment to ensure accuracy, relevance, and cultural sensitivity in future educational materials.
5. For local government and community leaders to use the insights from the needs assessment to support initiatives that promote local history and cultural heritage education, and to advocate for the development of relevant learning resources.
6. For future researchers to build on this study by exploring how the identified topics and cultural heritage elements can be effectively transformed into learning

materials, and evaluate their impact on students' cultural awareness and identity formation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study followed ethical guidelines, which are paramount, especially possible conflicts of interest. The researcher is committed to maintaining objectivity and ensuring that personal beliefs or affiliations do not influence the research process or its outcomes. It includes avoiding or being transparent about any potential biases or conflicts that may arise from the researcher's role as a teacher or member of the community. All sources used in this study are properly acknowledged and cited using a recognized referencing style to ensure transparency and respect for intellectual property.

Furthermore, the researcher guarantees that the study adheres to all ethical guidelines for research involving participants, particularly those related to informed consent, confidentiality, and data privacy, and the participants are fairly compensated for their time, effort, and any potential risks associated with their participation in the research. Data anonymization techniques were employed to remove identifying information wherever possible. They were informed that they had the absolute right to withdraw from the study at any point without threats or negative consequences. In case of withdrawal or refusal to participate, respecting their decision and safeguarding their autonomy is crucial. Upon completing the data gathering, participants will receive a token of appreciation for their involvement. By adhering to these ethical principles, the researcher ensured that the study was conducted with integrity and respect for human dignity. It enhances the credibility and value of the research findings.

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